

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MOTHER TONGUE TEACHING

Rakhimova Altin Kadambayevna

Urgench Innovation University

Teacher of the Faculty of Social Humanities and Pedagogy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10203528>

Abstract: The article examines the use of innovative educational technologies in teaching the mother tongue. In this article, the use of innovative technologies in mother tongue lessons, interactive methods during the educational process, increasing interest in the use of pedagogical and information technologies during the process of educational lessons, and the further formation of the teaching process of the mother tongue subject is waiting for its proof. A number of current problems and shortcomings are fully described.

Key words: native language, innovative, technology, educational technologies, interactive, method.

INTRODUCTION

During today's educational process, the desire and attention to use interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogic and information technologies during the course of educational lessons is increasing day by day. In this process, the teacher creates an environment for the student's personal improvement, development, learning and education, and therefore also performs the function of management and direction. Innovation (English innovation) is innovation. Innovative technologies are a pedagogical process, as well as introduction of innovations and changes to the teacher's activity, and interactive methods are widely used in its implementation. Interactive methods are called group thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of the educational content.

Today, large-scale work is being done to increase the position and prestige of the Uzbek language in society in all fields. Decrees and decisions adopted by our state on reforms in the socio-political and spiritual spheres, including the organization of educational work based on the needs of the times, improvement of the spheres of culture, art and literature, improvement of reading culture, Uzbek language, in particular, it serves the development of the mother tongue.

A number of current problems and shortcomings are still waiting to be solved in the teaching of the mother tongue as a science. For example: in the teaching of the subject of the mother tongue, attention is mainly focused on theoretical information, and insufficient attention is paid to improving the student's speech (listening, speaking, reading, writing) competence; the presence of many grammatical topics that are difficult for the student when the topics taught in the subject of the mother tongue are analyzed in the cross-section of classes; no attention has been paid to connecting the science of the mother tongue with life, making use of the rich opportunities of our mother tongue, and delivering it to students in a meaningful, simple, and interesting way; exercises and tasks that create interest, passion, inclination, encourage logical, creative, and creative thinking in students' mastery of the

topics in the textbooks are not reflected; new, effective methods of teaching the subject of the mother tongue in general secondary schools, wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies is not at the level of demand; scientific methodical support of mother tongue science (textbook, teacher's book, exercise book, multimedia applications, didactic materials, etc.) is insufficiently developed; improvement of methodical support of teachers and pedagogues, distance learning courses for teachers and methodologists of native language and literature have not been introduced; The fact that the quality of training of teachers, pedagogues, and personnel in the field of mother tongue science in existing higher education institutions does not meet today's requirements calls for a radical revision of the teaching of mother tongue science and updating it in accordance with the needs of the times.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of pedagogical technologies is to ensure that the teacher and the student achieve the set goal in cooperation. In the educational process, students can think independently, work creatively, search, analyze, and draw their own conclusions. The teacher's ability to create opportunities and conditions for students' activities is considered the basis of the teaching process. Each lesson, subject, subject has its own technology. Today, among the well-known and widely used methods, "Brainstorming", "Cluster", "VENN diagram", "BBB", "FSMU" are showing their effective results in the course of the lesson.

Methods such as "Comparison method", "Circle method", "6x6x6" have their own role in ensuring the effectiveness of the lesson. In particular, it would be appropriate to use the "Comparison Method" to strengthen the subject after studying the life and work of Odil Yaqubov and Pirimkul Kadyrov in literature. For this, students are divided into three groups. For the first group, the life path of Odil Yaqubov and Pirimkul Kadyrov and their similarities, for the second group, their creative heritage and the heroes they created and their similar times, and for the third group, generalization of ideas about the ideas put forward in their works, the team is requested to be submitted in installments. Also, after learning the subject of "Secondary parts of speech" from the subject of the mother tongue, students are asked to write "I'm a filler!" based on the method of working in groups. will be assigned to create a creative text on the topic. This task can be done individually, small or individually, small or large groups. The text on the topic is provided by the students. Through this method, students' teamwork skills are developed, their memory is strengthened, their written or oral literacy is improved, and their ability to create a creative text is strengthened. In order to strengthen students' written speech and spelling literacy in mother tongue classes, it is possible to give a number of interesting tasks related to text creation. For example, in the process of passing the "Morphology" section, if students are given the task of creating a grammatical story based on each set of words, along with the growth of grammatical literacy, students' ability to logically observe will develop, and their creativity will increase. Innovative technologies increase the quality and efficiency of education, put the learning activity of students at the center of the educational process, and ensure the integrity of the educational process. A high-level indicator of the student's activity is the organization of educational and cognitive activities, the will and activity becoming the subject of the student's mind. In order to realize this goal, first of all, the teacher should be able to choose the methods that lead to the goal and ensure the integrity of the educational process. Incessant search for introduction of innovative technologies in the educational process, improvement of educational efficiency is becoming the need of today. Implementation of new methods in the educational process is one of the issues facing

pedagogues. In addition to giving other information during the lesson, if the teacher shows additional information on the Internet, multimedia programs, tables, etc. increases the interest of students, but also helps students to form their independent study at the required level, to master the subject as fully as possible. "Brainstorming". This attack can be used at the beginning of mother tongue and literature classes or anywhere. In this lesson, the problem is given to the students through brainstorming and is revealed through their thoughts. "Brainstorming" method is widely used in solving problems related to a topic. With the help of the "Brainstorming" method, it is possible to find several solutions to the problem.

CONCLUSION

In short, it is aimed at encouraging students to think independently, freely, to search, to approach each issue creatively, to feel responsibility, to analyze, and most importantly, to stimulate the student. increases interest. Innovative technologies further improve the quality and efficiency of education, help to increase the learning activity of pupils and students in the center of the educational process, and ensure the integrity of the educational process. A high-level indicator of the student's activity is the organization of educational and cognitive activities, becoming the subject of the student's consciousness of will and activity. To realize this goal, first of all, it is necessary for the teacher to be able to choose the technologies that achieve the goal, to ensure the integrity of the educational process. In addition to providing other information during the lesson, if the teacher shows additional information on the subject, such as Internet information, multimedia programs, tables, etc., it not only helps students to learn It increases the aspiration of students, but also helps students to develop their free reading at the level of demand, to fully master the subject as much as possible. As a result of the use of innovative technologies, the students' skills of free thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, stating their ideas, being able to defend them in a reasonable way, healthy communication, discussion, and debate will be improved and formed

References:

1. Aripova M., Nosirova Sh. Use of modern pedagogical technologies in teaching English //Modern education (Uzbekistan). – 2014. – No. 2.
2. Olimov S.S. THE INNOVATION PROCESS IS A PRIORITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES. – 2021.
3. ОЛИМОВ Ш.Ш., ХОДЖИЕВА М. Ш. Возможности применения педагогических технологий в образовательном процессе //Молодежь и XXI век2020. – 2020. – С. 228-231.
4. Olimov S. THE DIFFERENTIATION OF EDUCATION IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. 8 No. 11, 2020 Part II ISSN 2056-5852
5. Kh K. R., Shukurov R. S., Samadov S. S. The Inquiry On The Changes Of Relations Towards The Basics Of The Culture Of Healthy Life In The Students Of Elective Courses //International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies. – 2021. – T. 25. – №. 2. – С. 112-118